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**LEADERSHIP
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RESULTS**

EXPLORING ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

With the growing emphasis on education and talent development, academic self-efficacy has emerged as critical constructs in higher education research. Prior studies confirmed their positive effects on academic achievement and psychological development; however, empirical research on effective intervention strategies remains limited. This study aimed to assess the levels of students' academic self-efficacy, identify differences across students, teachers, and administrators, and explore the challenges students face. Using an explanatory sequential mixed-method design, quantitative data were collected through surveys on self-efficacy (learning ability, learning behavior), followed by qualitative interviews for deeper insights. Respondents included students, teachers, and administrators from selected universities in China and the Philippines. Findings revealed significant differences in perceptions among role groups: administrators rated students' capabilities higher, while students rated themselves lower, particularly in learning ability. Interviews highlighted key barriers including academic stress, limited teacher support, and insufficient resources. This study contributes by integrating self-efficacy frameworks providing empirical evidence for designing intervention programs. The results offer practical implications for policymakers, educators, and institutions in fostering students' confidence, resilience, and academic success.

Keywords: *academic self-efficacy, higher education, mixed method, intervention framework*

Introduction

Since the 21st century, as higher education had transitioned from an elite system to mass education, declining academic quality had become a global challenge. According to the 2023 World Bank report, only 41% of university students in low-and middle-income countries meet the "basic academic competency threshold" (reading, mathematics, and critical thinking), while even in high-income countries, this proportion remained below 67%. This phenomenon could be attributed to the collapse of academic self-efficacy: the former concerned students' belief systems about their learning abilities, which influenced goal setting, persistence, and coping strategies in adversity (Bandura, 1997). High levels of academic self-efficacy had been found to reduce academic burnout, test anxiety, and procrastination (Gao, 2020), and were positively correlated with subjective well-being and mental health (Ren, 2021).

Varied countries in Asia face unique challenges and opportunities in their higher education systems. Disparities were influenced by regional economic growth rates, investment in educational resources, and the degree of internationalization. Institute of Party History and Literature of the CPC Central Committee (2024) emphasized that education was an important cornerstone of national rejuvenation and social progress. There were multifarious ways of honing an individual to become fully and decently educated. Learning motivation and reinforcement of the positive learning behaviour to perform dutifully and consciously the academic tasks were necessary to substantiate the cooperative and inclusive activities that education played in the learning environment.

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Statement of the Problem

The main purpose of this study was to explore the extent of students' academic self-efficacy in higher education. Specially, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What was the level of academic self-efficacy of the students as perceived by the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Learning ability;
 - 1.2. Learning behavior?
2. Were there significant differences in the responses of the respondents in terms of their roles as students, teachers and school administrators?
3. What were the challenges faced by the students in their academic self-efficacy?
4. Based on the results of the study, what framework for the administration of intervention programs may be designed to improve academic self-efficacy of the students?

Methodology

Design. This study adopted a mixed method, using both quantitative and qualitative research approaches. The mixed method design used was the explanatory sequential research design wherein collection and analysis of data from both quantitative and qualitative approaches were done (Siedlecki & Sandra, 2020).

Sampling Technique.

The sample respondents and research participants from the selected universities were determined through quota sampling technique.

Table 1: Target for Quantitative Study

Respondent Schools	Teachers		Students		School Administrators	
	Population	Sample	Population	Sample	Population	Sample
University Bravo	25 est	23	100 est	80	7 est	6
University Charlie	22 est	20	90 est	73	7 est	6
University Alpha	20 est	19	80 est	66	4 est	3
TOTAL	67	62	270	219	16	13

Statistical Treatment.

To analyze the data gathered in this study, several statistical treatments were employed.

Descriptive statistics were first used to determine the mean and standard deviation for each dimension of academic self-efficacy (learning ability and learning behavior) as perceived by the respondents. To assess whether the data met the assumption of normality required for parametric tests, the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality was conducted. The Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to examine whether there were statistically significant differences in the respondents' perceptions across roles.

Results.

I. Respondents' Perception of Academic Self-Efficacy

Table 2: Overall Mean Score of the Respondents in term of academic self-efficacy

Variables	Student		Teacher		Administrator	
	M	Interp.	M	Interp.	M	Interp.
Learning Ability	3.06	Much Confidence	3.19	Much Confidence	3.34	Quite a lot of Confidence
Learning Behavior	3.03	Much Confidence	3.19	Much Confidence	3.28	Quite a lot of Confidence

Table 2 above presented overall mean scores of the respondents in term of academic self-efficacy. Overall, students displayed "Much Confidence" in their learning ability and learning behavior regarding in their academic self-efficacy. while teachers and administrators showed higher approval. This discrepancy suggests that students may have a relatively low level of self-perception, while external observers are more likely to perceive their motivation in the learning process. This suggests that educators need to focus on students' self-perceptions, further enhancing their self-confidence and self-awareness, thereby promoting overall academic development. Since learning ability and learning behavior determine students' academic performance, improving academic self-efficacy is crucial. This is consistent with the findings of Alhadabi & Karpinski (2020) and Wu et al. (2020), who found that academic self-efficacy is a strong predictor of academic achievement, measured through various indicators such as GPA and academic performance.

2. Differences in the responses of the respondents in terms of their roles as students, teachers and school administrators?

Table 3: Shapiro–Wilk Test for Normality per Role

Variable	Role	W Value	p Value	Normality Assumption
Learning Ability	Admin	0.881	0.04	Violated
	Student	0.942	< .001	Violated
	Teacher	0.973	0.172	Not Violated
Learning Behavior	Admin	0.913	0.13	Not Violated
	Student	0.965	< .001	Violated
	Teacher	0.96	0.039	Violated

The Shapiro–Wilk test was used to assess the normality of the distribution for each variable across the three respondent roles. Results indicated that many of the variables significantly deviated from normality, especially for student responses. Specifically, normality was violated ($p < .05$) in several cases, including *Learning Ability* for Admin and Student, *Learning Behavior* for Student and Teacher, and all roles for *Emotional*.

Table 4: Kruskal–Wallis Test Results on Learning Ability and Learning Behavior by respondents

Variable	χ^2	df	p-value	ξ^2	Interp.
Learning Ability	13.5	2	0.001	0.0435	Significant difference among the three groups
Learning Behavior	18.8	2	< .001	0.0604	Significant difference among the three groups

The Kruskal–Wallis test revealed statistically significant differences in how the three role groups, students, teachers, and administrators, rated students' learning ability ($p = .001$) and learning behavior ($p < .001$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

3. Challenges Faced by the Students in their Academic Self-Efficacy

Table 5: Summary of Themes for respondents

Theme	Representative Quote	Participant Group
Emotional & Energy Exhaustion	High-difficulty courses trigger self-doubt and avoidance, undermining confidence.	Students
Executive Function Difficulties (Procrastination/Time Mgmt)	Time management is challenging due to family role and campus responsibilities.	Students
Theory-to-Practice Transfer Difficulty	Students grasp theory but struggle in labs; real-world gaps require flexibility that confuses them.	Teachers
Contextual Pressures (Family/Peers/Digital Distraction)	Phone research drifts into social apps; peer/family pressure reduces focus.	Students
Weak Micro-Achievement Loop	Breaking goals into daily + weekly review improved math.	Students
Clear & Visual Instruction (Checklists/Questioning/Formative Feedback)	Task lists and checkboxes aid focus; slides + videos increase interest.	Students/Teachers

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Resource Integration & EdTech Enablement	Open repositories, virtual labs, and apps expand learning pathways.	Admin/Students
Practice-Oriented & Authentic Tasks	Successful code/experiments boost efficacy; simulated teaching builds confidence.	Students
Institutional Supports (Assessment/Tutoring/Mental Health)	Diversified assessment, tutoring centers, and counseling sustain learning.	Admin
Cognitive Engagement: Solid, Transfer Weak	Know theory but application lags; needs varied practice & context.	Teachers
Behavioral Engagement: Strong Extra Effort	Willing to put in extra effort; self-study even with limited seats.	Teachers/Students

4. Framework for the Administration of Intervention Programs to Improve Academic Self-Efficacy of the Students

The implementation plan is developed based on insights into factors influencing academic self-efficacy. Each component of the plan outlines key factors necessary to support the framework. For students, the focus is on building confidence and enhancing learning motivation; for teachers, it emphasizes fostering a supportive environment and providing academic guidance; and for administrators involved in policy development and implementation, it highlights formulating professional training policies and establishing specialized policies for mental health training, among others.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above research results, the researcher draw the following conclusions:

1. Students' self-evaluations of their learning abilities and behaviors were relatively conservative, remaining at a "Much Confidence". However, teachers and administrators were more positive about these aspects, with administrators in particular rating them at a "Quite a lot of confidence".

2. Since the null hypothesis was not met, this indicated that there were significant differences in the responses to the relevant questions among respondents with different roles. These findings suggested notable discrepancies in perceptions of students' academic self-efficacy among students, teachers, and school administrators, arising from differences in how each group viewed their respective roles and perspectives.

3. Interviews with various researchers revealed several challenges to students' academic self-efficacy, including emotional exhaustion, physical and mental fatigue, disorganization, learning disengagement, lack of motivation, reliance on a single teaching strategy, and the absence of clear instructional policies.

5. Since the intervention program was grounded in key research findings, it was emphasized that all of these thematic areas needed to be supported and strengthened in order to achieve optimal educational quality.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions, the following suggestions are made:

1. Given that academic self-efficacy can effectively promote students' understanding of course content, completion of coursework, and the effective use of learning strategies, thereby overall enhancing their autonomous learning ability and improving their learning behavior, teachers are advised to adopt a variety of learning strategies in their teaching.
2. Given that students, teachers, and school administrators often have significant discrepancies in their perceptions of students' academic self-efficacy due to differences in their roles and perspectives, it is recommended that school administrators establish a diversified academic self-efficacy assessment system.
3. Given that a lack of communication between students and teachers can lead to misaligned understandings, differing definitions, and varying pressures, resulting in significant differences in learning engagement between students and teachers, schools are advised to strengthen communication and feedback mechanisms between students and teachers.
4. Given that this intervention project is based on key research findings, considering all elements of the proposal, it can be inferred that its feasibility is guaranteed to be effective.

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